

The Emergence of E-Commerce in India with Special Reference to Amazon and Flip Kart

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 2

Month: November

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2321-788X

E-ISSN: 2582-0397

Impact Factor: 3.025

Citation:

Archana, A.,

C. .. Bhavyashri, et al. “The Emergence of E-Commerce in India with Special Reference to Amazon and Flip Kart.” *Shanlax International Journal of Arts, Science and Humaities*, vol. 7, no. S2, 2019, pp. 53–58.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3669468>

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Abstract

Demands in the national and international market have led to various innovations in the fields of trade, i.e., buying and selling, the latest in this sector is the emergence of electronic commerce, also known as E-Business.

The growth of E-commerce has paved ways to many innovations in the fields of communication (M-Commerce), Transfer of funds (Electronic Fund Transfer), distribution of goods (Supply chain Management), and promotion of products. Flip kart and Amazon are the by-products of E-Commerce; these two companies are the pioneers of online marketing of our country. These companies have popularized the concept of E-Commerce, i.e., online promotion, buying, and selling, and both the companies have their strategies and techniques to reach out to the customer.

Since the Indian market is the huge one, it has given place, value, and profit to so many companies.

This study is to evaluate the E-Commerce techniques and strategies

Flipkart and Amazon

The conclusion of the study would is to know what measures would provide Flipkart and Amazon an edge to retain its market share.

Introduction and History: 102 Years (1916-2018)

E-commerce is introduced 100 years ago, and, to this day, continuous to develop with modern creativity, innovation, and giving the opportunity for many companies entering the online business platform regularly. The features of E-commerce have improved exponentially since its inception in the 1970s.

1960-1982

Paving the way for technology gave raise to E-commerce which introduced digital transfer of information from one party to another. Turning points in this period (1960-1982)

- a. Michel Aldrich, an English inventor, innovator, and entrepreneur, is credited with the development of the predecessor to online shopping.

- b. ‘Teleshopping’ was introduced by Aldrich in 1979. Teleshopping came into existence when he connected the T.V set, a transaction processing computer to a telephone line.

1982-1990

In the beginning, the B2B was very successful and profitable but B2C was not successful until the later widespread use of PCs and the World Wide Web, also known as the internet.

Major happenings in this period (1982-1990)

- a. In 1982, France launched a precursor to the internet called Minitel.
- b. By 1999, over 9 Minitel terminals had been distributed and were connecting approximately 25 million users in this interconnected network of machines.

1990 - 2018

The period of the ‘90s saw the changes in various fields, which contributed to the growth of online trade. Changes such as

- a. In 1990 Tim Berners Lee and Robert cailliau, came ahead with the idea of hypertext project called “World Wide Web”.
- b. Till 1991 use of net was under the control of National Science Foundation, but when the control was reduced. Net was used for commercial purpose. It is at this point inter grew and online shopping also expanded.
- c. In 1992 a book ‘Future shop’ was published which gave an idea of how the future of market can be.

From the time, online shopping was started there were many doubts in the minds of the users, but when safety measures were introduced, the users were quite assured and they started extensive usage of online shopping.

The mid-nineties to 2000s saw necessary advancements in the commercial use of the Internet. Between 2010-2018 there is a remarkable increase in the number of companies in the world as well as in India.

Top E-Commerce Companies

India	World
Flipkart Internet Private Ltd.	Amazon
Amazon Development Centre India Private Ltd.	Alibaba
Jasper InfoTech Private Ltd (Snapdeal.com)	eBay
One97 Communications Ltd (Paytm)	Rakuten
eBay India Private Ltd	Zalando
Clues Network Private Ltd (Shopclues.com)	Groupon
MakeMyTrip India Private Ltd	Flipkart
Yatra Online Private Ltd	ASOS.com

Objectives of the Study

- To study E-Commerce, Amazon and Flipkart in India
- To evaluate E-Commerce practices in Amazon and Flipkart
- To know the SWOT of Amazon and Flipkart
- To compare their promotional strategies
- To provide suggestions and recommendations

E-commerce in India

E-commerce has become very popular in India, like all the other countries E-commerce is used for buying, selling, distribution, exchange of trade related information, digital fund transfer and payment.

India first came into interaction with online E-commerce via the IRCTC. The Indian government introduced its online strategy for the public IRCTC for reservation of train ticket providing convenience to the ticket bookers. This is a huge achievement in the history of India in the field of online E-Commerce.

Amazon and Flipkart in India

Amazon.com, Inc., Amazon is an American multinational technology company based in Seattle, Washington. Amazon is one of the huge company in the world with broad customer base, AI assistance provider, and cloud computing platform, as measured by revenue and market capitalization. It is the largest internet company by revenue in the world. Amazon is the second-largest technology based company earning profit. The Amazon.com website started as an online bookstore and later diversified to sell video downloads /streaming, MP3 downloads/streaming, downloads/streaming, video games, electronics, apparel, furniture, food, toys, and jewelry.

The company took its first steps into the Indian market in February 2012 when it launched Junglee.com, a site that allowed customers to compare prices online but not purchase items directly.

It will initially only sell books, films, and TV shows but plans to offer mobile phones and cameras within weeks.

Flipkart - Flipkart is an Indian e-commerce company based in Bangalore, India. In 2007 Sachin Bansal and Binny Bansal started Flipkart after working with Amazon and after gathering lot of experience. The first product of Flipkart was book and later on they introduced consumer electronics along with many other products. Map my India was introduced by them in 2015.

E-Commerce practices of Amazon

Amazon acquired many companies including existing and new ones to offer economic prices for the products. Amazon’s strong customer-centric approach to analyses customer buying behavior based upon preferences has helped them to have a better edge over their competitors. Most of the Amazon customers remain loyal to them and hence the company is able to expand throughout the world.

Strengths of Amazon

Amazon has become a world-wide accepted company due to its policies, availability of variety of products, services, loyal customers, economical prices, wide distribution network and strategic alliances.

Weaknesses of Amazon

1. Shrinking margins
2. Tax Avoidance issue
3. High Debt: Product flops

Opportunities for Amazon

1. Backward Integration
2. Global Expansion
3. Acquisitions

Threats of Amazon

1. Low entry barriers of the industry
2. Government regulations
3. Local competition

Tagline: Amazon hai, Apna Dukaan

E-Commerce Practices of Flipkart

Leading the E-commerce giant of India, Flipkart has 75 million registered users who had helped the company to achieve 5 billion dollars GMV (Gross merchandise value) of sales in FY15. GMV is the indicator of the performance of the company in terms of the total cost of products sold by the company during the period. Its’ “Big billion days” is the most successful campaign which has resulted into the great profits for the company.

Flipkart divided the market and took care of particular needs and requirements of their customers. Flipkart has position itself as a responsible and customer friendly E-commerce brand.

Strengths of Flipkart

1. Flipkart is India’s largest E-commerce company
2. The Founders have experience of working in Amazon which has resulted in huge success of Flipkart.
3. A series of acquisitions have helped the company to expand in the E-commerce space.
4. Brand activities like the “Big Billion days” have increased the brand recall of Flipkart.
5. Flipkart has its Payment gateway & Logistic arm, thereby passing the benefits to the end customers.
6. Flipkart has Exclusive rights to launch & a broad range of its products:

Weaknesses of Flipkart

1. Limited Distribution channel reach
2. Cost of Acquisition
3. Power in the hand of buyers

Opportunities of Flipkart

1. Expansion of business
2. Expanding their Product categories
3. Changing the mentality of Indian customers
4. Establishing in other developing economies

Threats of Flipkart

1. Competition
2. Government regulations

Tagline- “Flipkart Matlab bilkul pakka.”

The following figure shows amazon has increased the investment in the past 6 years and Amazon has improved its integrating strategies, several targeted online marketing channels, such as Associates program, sponsored search, social and online advertising, television advertising, and other initiatives.

Comparison of Amazon and Flipkart Strategies

Amazon	Flipkart
Offering the expanded range of products	Expanding into nonmetropolitan India
Using a customer-friendly interface	Social Media and mobile technologies
Scaling likely from small to large	Diversified into electronic goods
Exploiting affiliate products and resources	Designing and delivering value propositions to Customer
Using existing Communication systems	Defining customer Experience
Utilizing universal behavior and mentalities	Connecting a customer needs with his experience
Acquiring IT and Commerce	Personalization of Products
Low Pricing	Products will be packed with new features like tamper-proof, weather proof, and breakage proof.
Public relation	Thirty days replacement and guarantee for faulty products.

Recommendation and Suggestion to Amazon

1. Amazon should concentrate more CSR activities to improve its image.
2. To meet competition, Amazon is regularly reducing the prices of its products leading to decrease in its profits. Hence it is suggested to Amazon to stress more on its strengths that are on product differentiation and repeatedly buying the customer.
3. The Branches of Amazon are regularly facing losses in all its markets; thereby, it suggests that Amazon concentrates more on the countries where they have already established themselves.

Recommendation and Suggestion to Flipkart

1. The Distribution network has helped Amazon to maintain low cost, but has resulted in not able to reach all the places, where Flipkart has an edge over to reach throughout the area.
2. To meet the competition, Flipkart is spending more money in acquiring new companies which has resulted in loss. Hence it is suggested that Flipkart concentrates more on its strengths rather than spending money on acquisitions.
3. Since this industry is overflowing with many players and where buyers have a lot of options to choose, Product differentiation, which is required, is almost absent in Flipkart. Hence it is suggested that Flipkart works more on product differentiation rather than working on pricing strategy.

Conclusion

Hence, it can be concluded that with the advancement of technology, E-commerce is going to evolve and expand. The advancement in the technology has erased all the gaps existed between the buyers and the sellers. In fact, it is observed that new unique features are introduced for better after sale services. There would be more companies like Amazon and Flipkart in the coming future.

Reference

1. <https://www.softwaresuggest.com/blog/E-Commerce-in-india/>
2. <https://www.scribd.com/doc/54549535/History-of-E-Commerce-in-India>
3. <https://www.bigcommerce.com/blog/beat-Amazon-best-practices-infographic/>
4. <https://stories.Flipkart.com/Flipkart-marketplace-innovation/>
5. <http://www.fortuneindia.com/technology/Flipkart-vs-Amazon/101198>
6. <http://www.differencebetween.info/difference-between-Flipkart-and-Amazon>